

VERY HIGH CYCLE FATIGUE OF FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES: AN ALTERNATIVE EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

T. J. Adam*, P. Horst

Institute of Aircraft Design and Lightweight Structures, Technische Universität Braunschweig,
D-38108 Braunschweig, Germany

* Corresponding author (tj.adam@tu-braunschweig.de)

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Abstract

A special test rig for high frequent four-point bending of fibre-reinforced flat specimens has been developed and combined with several online monitoring techniques. By circumventing common problems, it allows the detailed investigation of the degradation behavior, the damage mechanisms and their interaction at very high cycle numbers in the range of 10^8 . First data for a set of cross-ply $[0/90]_s$ GFRP specimens is presented. Analysis of stiffness degradation, crack densities and delamination give first insights in the effects of load level.

1 Introduction

As the majority of load bearing structures made from fibre-reinforced plastics (FRP) has to withstand vibrant, cyclic, highly dynamic or at least quasi static interval loads, fatigue is an important issue. Thus, and due to its complexity fatigue has been one of the main focuses in world-wide composite research since the 1960s. So far, a broad base of knowledge concerning the fatigue mechanisms, its dependencies as well as theoretical modeling approaches has been established. Experience ranges from static fracture to high-cycle fatigue between 1×10^6 to 1×10^7 load cycles. Thus, designing FRP structures able to safely withstand more than *high* cycle numbers usually leads to overly conservative designs. Typical applications reaching the so-called *very high cycle fatigue* (VHCF) range are GFRP wind turbine rotor blades (due to service times of up to 30 years) and light weight GFRP compressor blades of aero engines (due to frequency). However, despite its relevance, the very high cycle fatigue behavior of FRP has not been sufficiently investigated yet [1].

This recent work presents an alternative experimental approach to VHCF of FRP trying to

circumvent the common difficulties and to setup a testing environment which

- provides short testing times by testing at elevated frequencies between 50 - 80 Hz
- avoids thermal heating without being limited to extremely thin laminates
- provides several online damage monitoring techniques
- allows to investigate the degradation behavior, the damage mechanisms, the phenomenology and the dependencies in VHCF.

1.1 Available VHCF Knowledge

An early and comprehensive series of tests regarding the long-term fatigue of wind turbine materials has been conducted by Mandell *et al.* [2]-[4] in the 1990s. Most tests within the U.S. Department of Energy's (DOE) Wind Energy Program were constant-amplitude cyclic stress against cycle to failure (SN) tests of common test cupons. Furthermore, a high-speed procedure allowing tests with frequencies up to 100 Hz was developed. More recent VHCF studies analyzing the effect of stress level on the growth rates of transversal matrix cracks and delamination have been published by Hosoi *et al.* [5]-[9]. According to Hosoi *et al.*, tensile load amplitudes below 30 % of the static failure stress shifts failure into the VHCF range. A change in the order of appearance of transversal cracks and interlaminar delamination is observed as well. Neither matrix cracking nor delamination can be found up to cycle numbers of 2.0×10^8 when stress amplitudes are lower than 20 % of the static strength. Hosoi *et al.* reveal that the change in fatigue damage growth behavior is caused by different growth rates of cracking and delamination at each stress level. One essential

finding which has been commonly stated by Hosoi *et al.*, Mandell *et al.* and Apinis [10] is, that fatigue does not depend on frequency as long as temperatures are kept low.

All in all, knowledge is rare compared to the LCF and HCF range and a comprehensive investigation of the damage evolution, the mechanisms and the phenomenology in VHCF is long overdue.

1.2 Challenges for VHCF Testing

As already summarized by Mandell *et al.* [2] several difficulties and requirements concerning the testing equipment, the specimens as well as the damage monitoring have to be solved when testing in the VHCF range. The main problems directly result from the material properties of FRP. In contrast to metals, polymers have significant higher dampings and thus suffer from overheating when being tested at high frequencies. As high temperatures weaken the fatigue strength [11], temperatures have to be kept far below the glass transition temperature. Generally, in the previous studies this was overcome by limiting specimen thickness (Mandell *et al.*: $t = 1.5$ mm and fibre strands, Hosoi *et al.*: $t = 1.1$ mm). In addition to overheating the measurement of stress parameters by means of strain gauges or extensometers does not work for high cycle numbers or high frequencies. Another side effect resulting from the high in-plane fibre-parallel tensile stresses of FRP is the self-fatigue of standard servo-hydraulic testing machines.

2 Experimental Methods and VHCF set-up

Testing of FRP in the VHCF range is challenging for both, the specimen design as well as the testing equipment. Thus, a special test rig circumventing the main difficulties has been set up [6]. Its basic idea is that the heat transfer problem within the specimens can be solved by simply not stressing all laminate sections equally. In other words, *bending* which mainly stresses exterior layers is the most favorable load case for VHCF-testing. Indeed, even if bending fatigue may not be a typical widespread service load case, the exterior layers are mainly stressed by tension, compression or both. Thus, a technical relevancy is given. After having tried several high-frequency bending configurations in extensive pre-tests [12], four-point bending turned out to be the most promising load case, especially due to the constantly stressed middle part of the specimen as depicted in Fig. 1. Compared to two- or three-point bending, this configuration provides excellent damage monitoring possibilities. In contrast to axial testing, temperature only rises about 10 °C relative

to ambient temperature (for cross-ply lay-up) without additional cooling. Furthermore, comparatively low loadings positively impinge on the equipment's self-fatigue. However, there are difficulties as well. As bending requires rather large deflections (up to $d_a = \pm 5$ mm), relatively high accelerations have to be maintained continuously. This is a major problem for most actuator systems. For example, shaker actuators are optimized for high loadings and have large inner moving masses limiting accelerations and bringing up the need for cooling and maintenance. Another problem is the surface contact of the load introducing parts and the specimen. Surface friction has to be kept low to prevent local damage due to wear and heating.

Fig. 1: Geometric set-up for four-point bending equation, amplitudes of force f_a and deflection d_a

2.1 Test Rig for VHCF Four-Point Bending

The test rig (Fig. 2) is based on a simple, durable and high-frequency capable mechanic mounted onto a vibration-free base of steel and concrete. An independent VHCF unit (two are already in service, two additional are planned) can be seen on the left side of Fig. 2. It is driven by a customized electrodynamic actuator (1) allowing frequencies of up to 80 Hz (non-resonant), depending on the specimen configuration. A flat bending specimen ($t = 2$ mm, $w = 25$ mm, $l = 80$ mm) is embedded in a two-sided light-weight four-point bending device ($R = -I$) detailed on the right. Eight rotatable low-friction trunnions (four on each side of the specimen) prevent frictional heating and abrasive damage of the specimen. All four bearings are adjustable to specimen thickness. With the middle part of the device deflected via a light-weight actuator rod, a sinusoidal bending load is applied. Both parameters load (one load f on each side of the device) and maximum deflection d_a are measured online by means of two load cells and a triangulation laser directly pointing on the center point of the specimen. A control circuit in Lab View® provides

force control and displacement control. For the tests, an initial deflection (belonging to the desired stress level) is preset. Then, the resulting force is saved as reference load and maintained constantly by the controller. For degrading specimens, force control leads to increasing displacement amplitudes.

Another aspect is the control of ambient temperature. As bending forces are relatively small ($30\text{ N} \leq f_a \leq 500\text{ N}$) and as most light-weight devices are made of aluminum, changes in ambient temperature have undesired effects. Therefore, the rig is housed in an air-conditioned chamber with an air temperature of approximately $20 \pm 1.5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Even though the cooling cycles can be identified in the force signal, the effect is negligible over time. An insight into the test chamber is given in Fig. 3.

2.2 Damage Monitoring and Evaluation

It is well known that clamping and unclamping a specimen in the course of a test has undesired effects. Thus, online techniques (the authors declare all techniques which do not require specimen removal as online techniques) are preferred. Three systems have been integrated directly into the test rig (Fig. 3).

Firstly, the loads and the bending deflection are monitored (Fig. 4). Therefore, the sinusoidal signals are sampled with rate of 2000 Hz. Amplitudes are detected constantly, averaged over a timespan of one second and finally they are monitored in a 300 load cycle interval. Simultaneously, the specimen's effective bending (secant) modulus E_{xb} is calculated by means of the 4-point bending equation (Fig. 5).

$$E_{xb} = \frac{f_a}{d_a} \frac{6}{wt^3} \left(\frac{1}{3} a^3 + \frac{1}{2} ba^2 + \frac{1}{8} ab^2 \right) \quad |1|$$

Concerning the load ratio of $R = -1$ all examinations are only conducted for one bending direction. As all specimens show equal damage growths on both sides this limitation is acceptable.

Secondly, two optical systems (thermography and OTLP, online transmitted light photography) are used to analyze matrix cracking and delamination. In contrast to infrared imaging which is mainly used to monitor delamination hot spots, OTLP allows the observation of delamination and matrix cracking. Like transmitted-light microscopy, it is based on a cold light lamp shining through the transparent specimen (GFRP). As the OTLP lamp is integrated in the moving part of the bending device and as the camera (Fig. 3) is located on the other side, specimen removal is not necessary. However, the test operation has to be stopped for picture sharpness. Transmitted light imaging is adequate for deriving phenomenological damage parameters such as crack densities and delaminated area fraction.

Regarding the calculation of crack densities, it has to be differentiated between longitudinal and transverse cracks. Often the crack density is defined as cracks per unit length $\rho = n/L$ (1/mm) which works well for longitudinal cracks and transverse cracks completely passing the specimen width. However, as free-edge initiated and slowly growing fatigue cracks do not cross the specimen width immediately, their influence on bending stiffness is smaller. Thus, in addition to the number of cracks, their lengths are determined as well for each OTLP image made for a distinct cycle number. Then, crack density is calculated by dividing the total crack

Fig. 2: Schematic Diagram of a VHCF testing unit with the four-point bending device (simplified)

Fig. 3: Overview of the VHCF bending test rig

length of all full and partial cracks by the product of specimen width and longitudinal window length.

$$\rho_{90^\circ} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n l_{\text{crack},i}}{w_{\text{specimen}} \cdot l_{\text{window}}} \quad [2]$$

As this crack density does represent all cracks regardless of the specimen side, it cannot be directly compared to the measured bending stiffness. In fact, as damage growths is rather similar on both sides it is assumed that dividing ρ_{90° by two is a tolerable simplification.

Concerning the analysis of delamination, debonded areas are measured by means of digital image analysis. However, in the recent work this is complicated by widely scattered areas of small delaminations.

Fig. 4: Exemplary curves of the two load signals f_1 , f_2 (N) the total bending force f (N) and the bending deflection d_a (mm) for a degrading laminate

Fig. 5: Exemplary curve of the effective bending modulus E_{bx} , calculated with the four-point bending equation, the specimen geometry and the force- and deflection values

2.3 Specimen and Testing Parameters

All GFRP specimens ($1 \times w \times t = 80 \times 25 \times 2$ mm) are made from glass fibre rovings *Owens Corning OC111AX* (1200 tex) and a cold curing epoxy system *Momentive RIM135/RIMH137*. The configuration tested in the recent work is a cross-ply $[90/0]_s$ of four layers with the transversal plies as outer layers. With a laminate thickness of 2 mm each single layer is 0.5 mm thick. An average fibre volume fraction of $V_f = 0.40$ is determined by incineration. As sewing threads are imperfections causing inner heating (at higher frequencies) and as they affect the crack and delamination observation as well, the laminate is produced unsewn by CNC roving stacking and RTM. After cutting, all edges are polished to remove initial micro cracks. Due to the absence of sewing threads, the laminate nearly is transparent. All tests are constant load amplitude tests conducted at a moderate testing frequency of 50 Hz. For a first test series, ten specimens are tested at three different load levels as given in Tab. 1. These values have been calculated analytically by means of the four-point bending equation as well as the laminated plate theory for each specimen thickness and width before the tests. In each case, an initial deflection d_{a0} is preset to reach an initial maximum strain $\varepsilon_{22,0}^{90^\circ}$ and the corresponding stress of $\sigma_{22,0}^{90^\circ}$ in the transversal direction of the 90° -plies. Specimens number 003 and 010 are tested at a maximum initial surface strain of $\varepsilon_{22,0}^{90^\circ} = 0.44\%$ exceeding the average strain to rupture of $\varepsilon_{22,c}^{90^\circ} = 0.40\%$ (obtained from quasi-static tests). The second load level (specimens 005 and 002) is settled sharp below the breaking strain and the lowest level (specimens 001, 004, 006, 007, 009 and 012) has an initial surface strain of $\varepsilon_{22,0}^{90^\circ} = 0.26\%$.

	label*	d_{a0}/mm	$\varepsilon_{22,0}^{90^\circ}/-$	$\sigma_{22,0}^{90^\circ}/\text{MPa}$
1	A4PB-001	1.75	0.0026	22.79
2	A4PB-004	1.78	0.0026	22.73
3	A4PB-006	1.75	0.0026	22.73
3	A4PB-007	1.75	0.0026	22.84
4	A4PB-009	1.77	0.0026	22.79
6	A4PB-012	1.74	0.0026	22.86
7	A4PB-005	2.60	0.0037	32.32
8	A4PB-002	2.50	0.0037	32.56
9	A4PB-003	3.00	0.0044	38.72
10	A4PB-010	3.10	0.0044	38.69

Tab. 1: Overview of specimens and initial load parameters

*: alternating four-point bending (A4PB)

3. Experiments

At first, general observations made for all stress levels will be discussed. Then, differences between the stress levels are going to be revealed.

3.1 General Observations

In all cases transverse cracking and interlaminar delamination are the major damage mechanisms. Figure 6 shows a typical OTLP image of the constantly stressed middle section of a specimen. As the load ratio is $R = -1$ (bending is conducted to both sides) both outer 90° -layers are damaged equally. In the image both types of cracks (front side cracks, back side cracks) can be distinguished by their contrast. Concerning the transverse cracks, it is observed that they mainly initiate at the free edges. After initiation they grow across the specimen width and the ply thickness. This typical process is well known from axial tests in literature (e.g. [13]), especially for relatively thick plies (0.5 mm). Dependencies concerning the crack growth rate and the longitudinal crack spacing are observed for all specimens. For example, crack growth slows down when the crack density increases or when two crack tips overlap and restrain each other. This has e.g. been reported by Boniface and Ogin [14]. Furthermore, uneven crack planes and crack tip branching as depicted in the figure are typical phenomena. Whether there is an interaction between front side and back side cracks has not been

analyzed yet. With increasing cycle numbers, transverse cracking decreases and converges to a saturation crack density. The second damage mechanism which in all cases initiates after transverse cracking has progressed is delamination. However, no edge delamination occurs at all. $90^\circ/0^\circ$ -interface delamination areas are initiated locally when transverse cracks, growing in through the thickness direction, are stopped by the 0° -layer. Fig 7 A and B are offline edge micrographs showing transverse cracks with crack tip delaminations. For better visualization the specimen is four-point bent and side-lighted during imaging. Two different crack scenarios can be found. In the first case (A), the crack initiates and runs straight towards the interface. Here, by chance it splits at a resin rich zone before reaching the interface. There, a delamination initiates and grows along the interface. The second case (B) reveals the existence of cyclic tension-compression interaction. Due to the compression, a wedge-shaped fragment breaks away. In the further fatigue life, all delaminated areas grow along the width and length of the specimen, sometimes they coalesce, but they do not become global reaching from one transverse crack to the other. Concerning the material degradation, the typical decreases in stiffness as known from HCF (e.g. [15]) are observed. Generally, in a first range of cycles (depending on the stress level) there is a relatively steep decrease which then levels to a minimum between 80 % and

Fig. 6: Typical damage state of the constantly stressed section of a $[90/0]_s$ four-point bending specimen showing transverse cracking and scattered delamination

65 % of the initial stiffness. Transverse cracking turns out to be responsible for stiffness degradation at all stress levels. Delamination mostly occurs after main cracking and seems to have a minor effect.

One further observation is that none of the tested specimens reach final rupture, not even those tested at the highest stress level. As damage progression slows down significantly after the point of crack saturation, experiments have been stopped after a while. This behavior is presumably due to the laminate configuration. With the 90°-layers being fully degraded and the middle 0°-layers bearing the load the specimens become very flexible. Indeed, this state is reached for all stress levels. However, as the resulting maximum strain in the 0°-layers is smaller than the initial surface strains from Tab. 1, the onset of damage is probably a timely matter. None of the specimens tested showed the onset of longitudinal cracking even at 0.9×10^8 cycles. As final rupture does not occur, there is no *fatigue life*. Thus, cycle numbers cannot be normalized and the direct comparison of different load levels is vague.

Fig. 7: Edge micrographs showing transverse crack propagation and delamination in the 90°-layers

3.2 Higher Load Amplitudes

Two out of ten specimens (numbers 003 and 010) are tested at the highest load level with initial surface strains larger than the static fracture strain of 0.4 %. A third and a fourth one (specimen 002 and 005) are settled sharp below this value (see. Tab 1). Fig. 8 shows the decrease in bending stiffness normalized to the initial values. Data has been smoothed for better clarity. All specimens show a steep loss in bending stiffness forming a typical *elbow* within the first 0.5×10^6 cycles. In comparison with specimens 003 and 010 ($\sigma_{22}^{90^\circ} = 38.7 \text{ MPa}$), specimens 002 and 005 degrade slower due to a

lower stress amplitude ($\sigma_{22}^{90^\circ} = 32.6 \text{ MPa}$). However, compared to specimen 010, the stiffness decrease of specimen 003 is too slow as well as too small. All in all, degraded stiffnesses settle asymptotically in a range between 65 % and 75 %. No further degradation is measured up to 2.0×10^7 (010), 4.0×10^7 (002), 6.5×10^7 (003) and 7.0×10^7 (003) load cycles. Instead, some specimens show a slight increase in stiffness which seems to be due to internal friction effects with progressing damage state. Concerning the damage mechanisms, transverse crack densities for specimens 002, 003 and 010 are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 respectively. Overall, stiffness degradation is represented well. Regarding interlaminar damage, all highly stressed specimen show large amounts of delamination. However, measuring those scattered areas (compare Fig. 6) is rather imprecise and thus not conducted so far. Generally, delamination sets in during crack growth, but still in the very beginning before reaching crack saturation. As both load levels are settled in the region of static strain to failure, degradation behavior does not differ significantly.

3.3 Lower Load Amplitudes

Six specimens (001, 004, 006, 007, 009 and 012) are tested at fibre-orthogonal stress amplitudes of approximately $\sigma_{22}^{90^\circ} = 22.8 \text{ MPa}$ and initial strains of $\varepsilon_{22,0}^{90^\circ} = 0.26 \%$ which is about 60 % of the highest load level. As expected, degradation onset and progression is delayed. Fig. 10 shows the behavior of stiffness and crack density within the first 2.0×10^6 cycles. Obviously, stiffness decreases rather slowly not approximating a minimum value in this cycle range. Nearly all specimens show significant cycle lags in degradation onset. For example, degradation sets in at approximately 3.0×10^4 cycles for specimen 001, at 5.6×10^4 cycles for specimen 007, at 1.4×10^5 for specimen 012 and not before 2.7×10^5 cycles for specimen 006. In fact, there are scattered incipient cracks. Specimen 012 for example has a crack density of $\rho_{90^\circ}(1.4 \times 10^5) = 0.045 \text{ 1/m}$, however the effect is too small to be measured. The differences in cycle numbers to degradation onset are very likely due to material inhomogeneity. Concerning the further degradation Fig. 11 shows the cycle range up to 1.0×10^8 cycles. It can be seen, that the spreading in initial degradation behavior still is present at higher cycle numbers. Although the slopes differ, most degradation curves seem to have same tendencies. Unfortunately, not all tests could have been run to high cycles (12 days for 0.5×10^8 cycles at 50 Hz).

Fig. 8: Stiffness degradation and transverse crack density for high load levels, 0 to 2×10^6 cycles

Fig. 9: Stiffness degradation and transverse crack density for high load levels, 0 to 8×10^7 cycles

Fig. 10: Stiffness degradation and transverse crack density for low load levels, 0 to 2×10^6 cycles

Fig. 11: Stiffness degradation and transverse crack density for high load levels, 0 to 8×10^7 cycles

Fig. 12: Damage growths (binary images) of specimens 009 ($\sigma_{22}^{90^\circ} = 22.8$ MPa) and 002 ($\sigma_{22}^{90^\circ} = 32.6$ MPa) for similar cycle numbers

3.4 Effect of Load Level

Although the number of specimens tested is too small to derive founded results, first insights can be gathered. As expected and known from literature, the load level clearly affects the progress of damage and degradation. Regarding the cycle numbers, higher load levels lead to extensive transverse cracking and a steep loss of stiffness forming an *elbow* within the first 1×10^5 cycles. Stiffness minimum and crack saturation is reached within 1×10^6 cycles. In comparison, lower loads shift the point of crack saturation beyond 1×10^7 cycles. The elbow in stiffness loss is not that distinctive. A log-scaled comparison plot is given in Fig. 16. It is obvious, that most slowly degrading specimens neither reach the same minimum stiffnesses nor the equal crack densities as those being highly stressed. However, plotting degradation over crack density (Fig. 17) points out a rather linear damage-degradation relation with good agreement for all load levels (despite all simplifications and not taking into account delamination). Deeper analysis of the initial cracking by measuring crack lengths reveals differences in cracking behavior. Whereas higher loads induce transverse cracks directly crossing the specimen width (full cracks), lower loads lead to the initiation of many slowly growing small edge cracks (partial cracks). Fig. 13 shows the percentage of partial cracks for the first 1×10^5 cycles. In fact, specimen 004 and 012 do not show a single full crack (100 % partial cracks) up to 5×10^4 cycles. Contrary, specimens 010, 002 and 009 have a fraction of about 10 % to 20 % of full cracks at their first OTLP images. In the further degradation process the percentage of partial cracks decreases along with a growing number of full cracks and a reduced initiation of new cracks as depicted in Fig. 14. Regarding delamination, it has been observed that high loads lead to early delamination at the tips of transverse cracks reaching the 0° -layers. Although delamination areas have not been evaluated in detail yet, a tendency can be seen. Fig. 12 gives five OTLP binary pictures of specimens 002 (high stress) and 009 (low stress), taken at comparable cycle numbers. In contrast to specimen 009, first delaminations have been initiated in 002 before 5.0×10^4 load cycles. Then, at 7.0×10^5 cycles, specimen 002 already shows grown delaminations, even though crack saturation has not been reached at this state. This seems to be different for the low load level. Here, noticeable delaminations begin to grow with crack saturation. Micrographs of earlier crack states reveal, that crack growth in the thickness direction

of the 90° -layers is slow and thus delays delamination initiation. In Fig. 15, the onset of increased delamination growth is marked by circles to illustrate the observed tendency. However, the delamination behavior still has to be examined in detail.

Fig. 13: Partial Crack Fraction against load cycles for high and low load levels in the first 1×10^5 cycles

Fig. 14: Partial Crack Fraction against load cycles for high and low load levels up to 5×10^7 cycles

Fig. 15: Tendencies of distinct delamination onset

Fig. 16: Stiffness degradation and transverse crack density for all specimens, log scale

Fig. 17: Stiffness degradation plotted against transverse crack density for all load levels

4. Conclusion

An alternative approach to VHCF of fiber-reinforced composites is presented. It is based on a test rig specifically designed for high frequency testing of FRP and the idea that four-point-bending circumvents the problem of specimen heating. The approach allows constant load amplitude testing of 2 mm thick specimens at frequencies up to 80 Hz. Even thicker laminates are possible. Degradation behavior and damage mechanisms can be investigated by means of three online techniques (thermography, transmitted light imaging and online stiffness monitoring).

A first set of ten inverse cross-ply specimens [90/0]_s is tested at three load levels. Due to its 90°-layers primarily bearing the load, transverse cracking and delamination are the main damage mechanisms. As known from the HCF range, the degrading transverse layers lead to an overall decrease of bending stiffness in the early fatigue life. For the higher loads this decrease is within the first one million cycles. Testing at low loads extends the degradation up to 10 million cycles due to a different cracking behavior. Whereas for high loads transverse cracks cross the specimen width and ply thickness immediately, partial cracking prevails at lower loads. As cracks grow slower in thickness direction, delamination initiation is delayed. In comparison, most slowly degrading specimens neither reach the same minimum stiffnesses nor the equal crack densities as those being highly stressed. However, all specimens show agreeing damage-degradation relations.

So far, first insights have been gained. Upcoming experiments will have to be conducted

- for a larger number of specimens and at lower load levels
- up to higher cycle numbers
- with shorter OTLP intervals in the phase of increased degradation
- for several laminate configurations including regular cross ply and angle lay-ups

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